

Figure Z4

Figure Z4: Integration of this study with tissue-matched publicly available single-cell studies. (A and B) Single-cell clustering of 144,727 cells from this study and GSE133486. The UMAP plot is coloured by study (**A**) and cell type (**B**). (**C and D**) Single-cell clustering of 78,150 cells from this study and GSE150065. The UMAP plot is coloured by study (**C**) and cell type (**D**). A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods. Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) was used to integrate the datasets.